

FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE SKILL OF READING IN THE YOUNGER SCHOOL AGE

Ahunjanov Ibragim¹

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the peculiarities of the formation of reading skills in primary school age, analyzes the pedagogical conditions for the formation of reading skills as a factor in the success of younger schoolchildren. For the formation of reading skills in literary reading classes, special methods and techniques are distinguished by which younger students develop not only an automated ability to sound the text, but also a conscious perception of the read work that contributes to the formation of reading skills. The reading skill is a reading mechanism that consists of these components: correctness, fluency, consciousness and expressiveness. In order for some skills to develop, an automated skill has developed, it is not at all necessary to perform long-term exercises. The most important thing is that we need not a duration, but a frequency of training exercises. The daily work on the development of the skill of correct and fluent reading of a junior schoolchild should be carried out from the first grade on the lessons of literary reading. Only under such conditions can one develop a full-fledged reading skill and contribute to the literary development of younger schoolchildren. Thus, the work on the formation of the skills of correct, fluent and conscious reading of schoolchildren is carried out in indissoluble unity. This systematic work makes the lesson lively, interesting and informative for students.

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¹ Master, Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, UZB

Statement of the problem in general terms and its connection with important scientific and practical problems. Reading plays an important role in the mental activity of younger schoolchildren, the skills of which they master in the process of schooling. The process of reading for younger students is a complex and lengthy process that requires them to be patient, attentive and diligent in the classroom. Understanding of the read text occurs on the basis of the sound form of the word, associated with its meaning. These aspects are closely related to each other. Reading comprehension is determined by the nature of the perception of this or that information. In this regard, the problem of the formation of reading skills is relevant and important for the development of a harmonious personality of a younger student.

Analysis of recent studies and publications that dealt with aspects of this problem and on which the author bases himself; highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Both domestic and foreign psychologists and teachers are studying the problem of forming reading skills. S.A. Anichkin, V.G. Goretsky, O.V. Dzhezheley, L.F. Klimanov, Z.I. Romanovskaya, N.N. Svetlovskaya revealed the features of the development of reading skills and its formation in elementary school students. A.G. Asmolov, M.P. Voyushina, L.S. Vygotsky, A.A. Leontiev, L.A. Mosunova, T.D. Polozova, K.D. Ushinsky. These researchers studied the features of the formation and development of this process. The question of the technology of forming the skill of fluent, conscious reading among students was analyzed by S.N. Kostromina, A.M. Kushnir, L.G. Nagaeva, M.I. Omorokova

Formation of the goals of the article (setting the task). The purpose of the article is to reveal and analyze the pedagogical conditions for the formation of reading skills as a factor of success in educational activities.

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results.

Primary school education is based on reading lessons. Reading skill is the most important success factor in the process of teaching younger students. It has been noted that if a student has mastered the technique of reading, speaking and writing, and if he loves the lessons of literary reading, then he will successfully master other school subjects.

V. Sukhomlinsky also noted that "Reading is a window through which children see the world and themselves." Indeed, in the process of reading, the growth of self-consciousness, the formation of mental abilities, moral, patriotic and aesthetic development are carried out. Students have an interest in self-development, a desire to more accurately and competently express their thoughts, develop their speech.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account the features of the text being read in the formation of reading skills. The main thing is not to reduce the process of reading to meaningless voicing of written speech. Reading at the lessons of literary reading should be considered as an aesthetic activity, since primarily works of art are studied [1, p. 79]. Younger students should learn to highlight the semantic meaning in the text and express

their own thoughts based on what they read. The priority of reading as a speech activity does not lead to the development of reading skills, but, on the contrary, inhibits it.

“The skill of reading is one of the complex psycho-physiological processes. It intertwines elements and properties related to mental and speech activity. The reading process includes the personal qualities of the reader, his feelings, perception, attention, imagination, abilities, interests, values. The accumulated knowledge about the surrounding world is developing. Vocabulary is mobilized, the vocabulary that the reader owns, accumulated by him in the process of everyday speech, household, individual and collective forms of communication, the learned models of word usage, inflections and word formations, models of constructing a text, sentences are activated,” M.I. Omorokov [2, p. 74].

The formation of reading skills in a younger student has the following features:

- The reading field of the reader covers only one letter in order to “define” it, often he compares it with others; reading a letter awakens in the reader a natural desire to immediately pronounce a sound, but the teacher asks to pronounce a whole syllable, which means that he has to read at least one more letter, keeping the previous one in memory, he must merge two or three sounds into a syllable. This is where many students experience great difficulty. After all, to read the whole word, it is not enough to reproduce only the sounds that make it up. The process of reading is slow, because in order to read a word, you need to perform several actions of perception and recognition corresponding to the letters in the word, moreover, you still need to combine sounds into syllables, and syllables into words. The eyes of a novice reader lose the line, because he has to go back, reread the letters, syllables. His gaze is not yet accustomed to moving parallel to the lines. This problem gradually disappears as the scope of the student's attention expands, and he perceives at once a whole syllable or a whole word;

- a novice reader does not always quickly understand the meaning of the text being read. Much attention is paid to the technical side of reading, to each elementary action, and by the time the word is pronounced, the younger student does not have time to comprehend it. Awareness of the meaning is torn off from the process of reading, the "definition" of the word does not occur along with its reading, but after. Reading awareness is of great importance in elementary school. Consciousness of reading is increased through pictures, questions and explanations of the teacher, visual aids, reading texts aloud, since the auditory stimulus complements the visual perception of the word and helps to understand its meaning. However, weak reading consciousness is the most important difficulty in teaching literacy;

- it is common for a novice reader to guess words by the first syllable or by a picture, by context. These attempts to guess words quite often lead to errors in reading, but the student strives to read consciously. Such errors are corrected by immediate reading by syllables, sound-letter analysis and synthesis. A common difficulty in teaching reading is the difficulty of sound fusion: schoolchildren pronounce individual sounds, but cannot form a syllable. Syllabic reading is considered the most effective way to overcome the difficulties of

sound fusion. Attention to the syllable as a unit of reading can help in the learning process. [3, p. 127].

The perception of the text being read by younger students differs from the perception of an adult and has specific properties:

- fragmentation, lack of integrity of perception of the readable work;
- weakness of generalizing perception;
- lack of life experience;
- relationship with the practical activities of the student;
- pronounced emotionality and spontaneity, empathy;
- the predominance of interest in the content of speech;
- insufficient understanding of the expressive means of speech;
- the predominance of the reproductive level of perception of the child.

It is known that during primary school education, a younger student undergoes a transition to verbal-logical thinking, while visual-figurative thinking remains predominant at this age. It is difficult for a younger student to establish causal relationships, this is due to the peculiarity of this type of thinking. That is why it is easier for a child to determine temporary connections, and for the same reason there are difficulties that a child has in developing reading skills. At primary school age, semantic memory begins to actively form, requiring work aimed at understanding and thinking about the text.

Thanks to the improvement of semantic memory, an idea is formed about the readable work as a whole, which helps the student to determine cause-and-effect relationships in the text. In addition, it is difficult for younger students to single out individual components of the text for the next analysis - to identify the meaning of the desired episode, evaluate the actions and analyze the character of the characters, etc.

Conclusions of the study and prospects for further research in this area. Having analyzed the process of development of mental processes in younger schoolchildren, L.F. Obukhova is convinced that one should not build the entire process of developing reading skills, since children of primary school age already have a well-formed mechanical memory. In order for the process of forming the reading skill to be effective, it is necessary to pay attention to the zone of proximal development of the student, namely, to the formation of semantic memory and comprehension of the text [4, p. 198].

The process of developing reading skills is a complex, multifaceted process. First of all, this is the formation of the ability to understand the meaning of the read work, its content; correct reading - the ability to read words in such a way as to prevent omissions, permutations, substitutions, errors in them; expressiveness - the ability to correctly intonate punctuation marks, give the text emotionality, liveliness, pace - a certain reading speed [5-17].

M.I. Omorokova claims that the process of reading in younger students has the following stages of development: syllabic, syllable + word, word + syllable. At the first stage, the student sees the letter and translates it into sound. The better the younger student

knows the letters, confidently switches from one letter to another, the faster the reading process proceeds. The necessary way of reading is a slow, consistent pronunciation of the sounds corresponding to these letters [18, p.93].

The younger student performs the following procedure: analyzes the graphic image of the letter, translates it into sound, reads successively the syllables that make up the word, combines them into a word, understands its meaning.

The process of forming reading skills is characterized by the following conditions:

- in the formation of reading skills, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of such psychological processes as perception, attention, memory, thinking;
- the skill of reading is fixed much faster, develops when other types of speech activity develop along with it: listening, writing;
- reading lessons should be built in such a way that the content, forms and technologies of work in the lesson contribute to the formation of only positive motivation in younger students, interest in reading and in the book;
- the formation of reading skills should be considered as the goal of not only one lesson - a lesson in literary reading, but also as one of the goals of other lessons.

The process of formation of reading skills in younger students is quite slow, this is related to the peculiarities of its development and perception.

When forming a full-fledged reading skill for each student in the class, one should remember and strive for what Korf N.A., a brilliant Russian methodologist, calls us to. He noted that "each teacher should teach to simultaneously improve two processes - reading and understanding what is being read"[19, p. 182].

At the first stages of the formation of reading skills, the teacher should attach great importance to the technique of reading, and then to the comprehension of what has been read.

Thus, the reading skill consists of two most important components: the semantic component, which includes awareness and understanding of the text read, and the technical component, the essence of which is the correctness and expressiveness of reading.

The elementary school program provides for stage-by-stage training from class to class, and at each stage, the formation of reading skills is assessed according to such criteria and indicators as: the volume of what is read, correctness, awareness, expressiveness.

Currently, schoolchildren read little and without desire. This happens due to certain reasons, such as: lack of interest in reading, the advent of the Internet, gadgets, etc.

The process of forming reading skills is carried out in 3 stages: analytical, synthetic and automation stage.

At the analytical stage, the younger student learns to correlate sound and letter, learns to merge syllables, and then - to add words. The understanding of what was read in a given period is separated from the process of perception in time: the student first reads the word and only then realizes its meaning. Characteristic at this stage is "chopped" reading, in which words are read without intonation, pedagogical sciences by connecting to

each other. Errors in this period are: replacement of the endings of words and repetition of words. Sometimes a student himself notices his mistakes and tries to correct them, therefore, he moves to another stage in the formation of reading skills [20, p. 26].

The stage of synthetic reading is characterized by the fact that the word in the mind of the student is determined not simply by the union of individual parts, but acts as a whole. At the same time, the visual perception of the word coincides with the awareness of its meaning.

The period of synthetic reading lasts long enough. According to T.G. Egorov, it lasts at the stage of primary education, and for most schoolchildren it ends only in the middle school [21, p. 163].

At the stage of automating the reading skill, the formed skills are improved and consolidated. The technical side of reading gives way to the process of understanding the meaning and meaning of what is read.

An important sign of the student's transition to the stage of automation is his desire to read to himself.

Thus, in the process of teaching reading, the teacher should pay attention to helping younger students overcome problems at the analytical stage as quickly as possible and develop an interest in reading, forming the skill of automated reading.

The modern method of teaching reading defines the skill of reading as an automated skill for voicing a readable work, understanding the intent of the perceived text and forming a personal relationship to what is read. At the same time, such reading activity provides for the ability to reason about the text being read before reading, during reading and after. Only such "conscious reading" is a means of introducing the student to reading, personal development and immersion in the wonderful world of the book [22, p. 120].

Therefore, the formation of reading skills for younger students is an important factor in successful schooling. However, this requires systematic and purposeful work on the formation and improvement of reading skills.

References

1. Methods of teaching literature in elementary school: a textbook for students. Higher Proc. institutions [Text] / ed. M.P. Voyushina. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2010. - p. 79.
2. Omorokova, M. I. Improving the reading of younger students: a method. manual for the teacher / M. I. Omorokova; M-total and prof. education of the Russian Federation. - Moscow: Arkti, 1997. - p.74.
3. Lvov M.R., Goretsky V.G., Sosnovskaya O.V. Methods of teaching the Russian language in primary school. - M., 2010, - S. 127.
4. Obukhova L.F. Child psychology: Theories, facts, problems [Text] / L.F. Obukhov. - M.: Trivola, 1998. - p.198.
5. Practical methodology for teaching the Russian language in primary school. Part one. Literacy lesson. A lesson in teaching literary reading. - Tomsk: "Peleng", 2000 - 96 p.

6. Lanin B.A. Methods of teaching literature: Educational reader-workshop: For students of higher pedagogical educational institutions [Text] / B.A. Lanin. – M.: Eksmo, 2007. – 512 p.
7. Litvinova A.V. Peculiarities of the formation of the reading skill of younger schoolchildren / A.V. Litvinova, M.V. Moiseenko // Young scientist No. 1 (81) January. Ed. "Young Scientist" - 2015. - C. 21 - 23.
8. Lvov M.R. Methods of teaching the Russian language in elementary grades; Proc. allowance for students. Higher Ped. textbook institutions / M.R. Lvov, V.G. Goretsky, O.V. Sosnovskaya. - 2nd ed., Rev. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2000. - 464 p.
9. Lvov M.R. Methodology for the development of speech of younger students / M.R. Lvov. – M.: Enlightenment, 2007. – 176 p.
10. Methods of teaching literature in elementary school: a textbook for students. Higher Proc. institutions [Text] / ed. M.P. Voyushina. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2010. - 288 p.
11. Leontiev A.A. Language and speech activity in general and pedagogical psychology [Text] / A.A. Leontiev. - M.: Publishing House of MPSI, 2004. - 535 p.
12. Mishina I.N., Korosteleva E.Yu. Didactic means of forming skills and abilities for the development of speech of younger schoolchildren // Vector of Science of Togliatti State University.
Series: Pedagogy, psychology. 2012. No. 4 (11). pp. 196-198.
13. Zair-Bek, S.I. The development of critical thinking in the classroom: a guide for general education teachers. institutions [Text] / S.I. ZairBek, I.V. Mushtavinskaya. – M.: Enlightenment, 2011. – 223 p.
14. Nikitina. L.V. Improving the effectiveness of reading lessons by organizing group work. - 2011. - No. 5 - 102 p.
15. Svetlovskaya N.N. Reading Teaching Methods: What is it? // "Primary School", 2005. - No. 2 - 126 p.
16. Korosteleva E.Yu. Technology for the formation of skills and abilities in preschoolers and younger schoolchildren necessary for the development of speech // Vector of Science of Togliatti State University. Series: Pedagogy, psychology. 2011. No. 1 (4). pp. 92-96.
17. Klimanova L.F. Literary reading grades 1-4 / L.F. Klimanov, V.G. Goretsky, L.A. Vinogradskaya. M.: Education, 2012. S. 53-67.
18. Omorokova M.I. Improving the reading of younger students - M.: 2009., P.93.
19. Korf N. A. Russian elementary school: hands. for zemstvo vowels and teachers of rural schools. – Ed. 6th, corrected again. and additional - St. Petersburg. : Type of. M. A. Khana, 1879. - 283 p.
20. Methods of teaching literary reading: textbook for M545 stud. institutions of higher prof. education / [M.P. Voyushina, S.A. Kislinskaya, E.V. Lebedeva, I.R. Nikolaev]; ed. M.P. Voyushina. - 2nd ed., Rev. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2013. - .26.

21. Egorov T.G. Psychology of mastering the skill of reading / T.G. Egorov. - St. Petersburg: KARO, 2006. - P.163.

22. Lvov M.R. Methods of teaching the Russian language in elementary grades; Proc. allowance for students. Higher Ped. textbook institutions / M.R. Lvov, V.G. Goretsky, O.V. Sosnovskaya. - 2nd ed., Rev. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2000. - P.120.